

ECOBULK

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product

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Report on (re-)manufacture of the innovative wood based products.

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Executive Summary

As a composite wood based material, in line with Moretti design requirements, we aimed at manufacturing particleboard for furniture industry which is low (E0) in formaldehyde emission and has high re-manufacturing value.

Our first aim was to produce panels from non-formaldehyde resins or at least catch E0 formaldehyde emission level. Our second aim was to produce panels that are easily recyclable with high waste content, especially with high levels of particleboard waste.

Throughout our development activities almost 90 different binder formulations were evaluated. Of those formulations, promising ones were tested in Kastamonu Entegre Adana labs. These trials were made by virgin wood. Binder and chips were blended manually. Around 150 panels were produced and tested.

Wood waste used in particleboard manufacturing includes particleboard around 20% in Italy and it is much lower in other countries like less than 15% in UK. Best performing 5 formulation were tested with %100 waste content, simulating different percentages of waste particleboard. We were able to produce EN212 P2 and E0 emission level panels from 100% wood waste with even 50% particleboard waste percentage using our formaldehyde based resin NARY19007. This ensures higher level of utilization of particleboard panels in their end of life. We had promising results with non-formaldehyde resin KROL 19007 with some shortcomings in water resistance. As we overcome this minor obstacles, we will be able to manufacture non-formaldehyde wood based composite panel manufactured from 100% waste with high waste particleboard content.

During manufacturing activities, resins were developed by Akzonobel in small batches. We were able to produce 50cmX50cm panels in KEAS labs. We will produce 1.200mmX1.600mmX16mm panels in Fraunhofer WKI facilities with these two formulations. Those panels (if successful) will be used by Moretti in some part of their furniture design. This situation will not postpone Ecobulk furniture demo activities since KEAS can provide 100% recycled panels for Moretti for current design.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Description of the Document and Pursue

This deliverable defines activities done under WP4 regarding manufacturing composite wood-based furniture parts and assessing re-manufacturing properties of those parts.

1.2. WPs and Tasks Related with the Deliverable

This deliverable belongs to WP4 and core tasks are 4.2.2 and 4.2.5. Activities are highly correlated with WP3 activities especially with task 3.3.

2. Target Industries and Wood Waste Management in Europe

World production of furniture was worth US\$ 462 billion in 2019 (CSIL, 2019). Composite wood-based furniture parts are highly used in office, kitchen, bedroom, bathroom, living room and dining room furniture.

Two main composite wood-based products used in furniture industry are Particleboard and Medium Density Fiberboard (MDF). Particleboard is produced from wood particles while MDF is produced from wood fibers. Ecobulk concentrates on particleboard as a composite wood-based material.

First part of this section explains world furniture market and composite wood-based materials used in this market. Second part makes a brief look at wood waste management particularly composite wood-based products in selected EU countries.

2.1 World Furniture Market and Composite Wood Based Materials Used in Furniture

2.1.1 World Furniture Market

World production of furniture was worth US\$ 462 billion in 2019. The main furniture producer is China, with 39% of world furniture production. Other major furniture manufacturing countries are the US, Germany, Italy, India, Poland and Vietnam. European Union (EU28),

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Norway and Switzerland and Iceland production value is US\$ 105, which accounts for %23 of total world production (CSIL, 2019).

World Furniture Production Value

The main furniture exporting country is China, followed at a distance by Germany, Poland, and Italy. The leading importers of furniture are the United States, Germany, France and the United Kingdom (UN, 2018).

World Furniture Export

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World Furniture Import

2.1.2 Composite Wood Based Materials Used in Furniture

Composite wood-based furniture parts are highly used in office, kitchen, bedroom, bathroom, living room and dining room furniture. Particleboard and MDF are two main wood-based composites made from particles and fibres.

2.1.2.1 Particleboard

Particleboard

Particleboard is used as a generic term for any panel product that is made with wood particles. Of course, there is a great range of particle shapes and size used to make particleboards. The type of particle is therefore used to define the type of particleboard product. For example, following English terminology, chipboard is made with chips, a flakeboard with flakes, oriented strand board (OSB) with strands and so on (Heiko, 2010). Most European countries (as

we will also do in this report) use the term particle rather than chip and therefore particleboard as a term for chipboard.

History of particleboard (Thoeman, 2013).

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In particleboard manufacturing, wood particles are bonded together by adding a synthetic adhesive and then pressing them at high pressures and temperatures.

The main process stations in a Particleboard production line

2.1.2.2 Medium Density Fibreboard

MDF

Medium Density Fibreboard (MDF) was first developed in USA from hardboard manufacture. Hardboard is made via a wet process that is similar to paper manufacture and therefore produces a lot of polluted water that requires treatment before disposal. Semi-dry processes were developed in the 1950s and this led to a fully dry-process method. The first dry-process MDF factory was built in Deposit, USA, in 1965 and the first MDF factory in Europe is thought to be that built in the former German Democratic Republic at Ribnitz-Damgarten in 1973 (Williams, 1995).

History of MDF (Thoeman, 2013)

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MDF is a composite wood product composed of fine lingo-cellulosic fibres, combined with a synthetic resin and joined together under heat and pressure to form panels. The most commonly used lingo-cellulosic fibres are wood, but other plant fibres can be used, e.g. bagasse and cereal straws (Heiko, 2010).

The main process stations in an MDF production line

2.2.2.3 World Production of Particleboard and MDF

Use of Wood-based composites in furniture industry

Total world particleboard and MDF production is around 200 million m³. Asia (including China) produces 56% of this output. European production accounts for 31% of total world production (UN, FAOSTAT, 2017). Total market value is expected to be around 60 Billion US\$.

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World particleboard+MDF production, M3, 2017

China is worlds biggest particleboard and MDF producer. Germany, Russia, USA and Turkey are other big players.

Source: FAO, EPF

Source: FAO, EPF

Biggest Particleboard and MDF producers

2.2 Wood Waste Management in Europe for Selected Countries and Waste Wood Usage in Composite Wood Based Materials

2.2.1 Wood Waste Management in Europe

According to the statistic office of the European Union (Eurostat), Germany is the main producer of waste wood in Europe followed by France, United Kingdom, Italy and Finland. Based on the characteristics of the waste wood, it can be classified in four (4) categories: A I, A II, A III and A IV.

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Category	Description	Applications
A I	Untreated or only mechanical treated wood	Chips and Shavings to produce wood-based materials, synthesis gas and activated carbon production (possible energy)
A II	Glued or painted wood (No halogen-organic compounds or preservatives)	Chips and Shavings to produce wood-based materials, synthesis gas and activated carbon production (possible energy)
A III	Wood containing halogen-organic compounds; no preservatives	It can be used as material if the varnishes and coatings are removed
A IV	Contaminated Wood, including halogen-organic compounds No PCB	Energy use in large combustion facilities
Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCB)	PCB treated wood	Non-hazardous disposal

Recycled waste wood categories in Germany

2.2.1.1 Germany

According to the Federal Statistical Office, Germany produced 401 million tons of wastes in 2015, from which waste wood¹ accounts to 11.9 million tons (Philipp F. Sommerhuber a, Johannes Welling a, Andreas Krause b, 2015).

This waste wood is obtained from different sources such as wood packaging (21%), demolition and construction (26.7%), wood processing industry (14%), municipal wastes (20.7%), import wood (9.7%) and others such as private households and railway construction (8%) (Mark van Benthem, Nico Leek, Udo Mantau, Holger Weimar, 2007). Due to the low availability of "clean" waste wood, 20% of the recycled waste wood (mainly, A I and A II) is used to produce wood-based products (e.g. particleboards) and the remaining 80% (A III and A IV) is used to produce energy in incineration facilities (Philipp F. Sommerhuber a, Johannes Welling a, Andreas Krause b, 2015). An important factor that encourage the use of the waste wood for energy production is the sale price. Whereas the sale price of the A I waste wood for energy purposes ranges between 70 and 80 € per ton, the sale price of A I waste wood for particleboard production is approximately 60 € per ton (EUWID, 2017). Due to the high availability and low cost of contaminated waste wood, most companies prefer to burn these residues to produce energy instead re-using, cascading and improving their added-value. In following years, this scenario is going to change due to the implementation of the new Renewable Energy Act

¹ Waste Wood = Material before processing in recycling facility

Recycled Waste Wood = Material after processing in recycling facility.

(EEG 2017) in Germany that implements a quantitative control of the installed capacity for electricity generation from renewable energy sources (Carlos A. Garcia, Guido Hora, 2017).

2.2.1.2 United Kingdom

The annual production of waste wood in the United Kingdom accounts to 4.1 million tons (Circular Economy & Resource Efficiency Experts, 2011). This waste wood is obtained from construction (25%), demolition (26%), joinery & furniture (9%), packaging (27%), municipal (13%) (Department of Environmental and Rural Affairs, 2012). More than 50% of the recycled waste wood was destined to the panel board industry and for energy production, 25% was exported and the remaining was used for different purposes (e.g. animal bedding, mulches, composting, equine surfaces, and pathways and coverings) (Circular Economy & Resource Efficiency Experts, 2013).

2.2.1.3 Italy

The amount of waste wood generated in Italy from the wooden packaging industry accounted to 2.633.818 tons per year in 2014. Rilegno is the National Consortium for the collection, recovery and recycling of wood packaging that works within the system CONAI (National Packaging Consortium). The main task of Rilegno is to ensure the achievement of the objectives set by law for the overall recovery of the packaging timber after consumption such as pallets, crates, boxes, cages and cable reels. For this purpose, Rilegno has a well-established transportation network to collect these wastes in different municipalities from deposits by private operators in the industry as well as retailers (Carlos A. Garcia, Guido Hora, 2017).

The activities of Rilegno ensured 1.793.748 million ton of wood (mainly from packaging but also other end-of-life wood products) enter the recycling system in 2018. Rilegno has progressively increased the range of recovery operations on the territory, which today include also wood waste fractions different from packaging waste, boosting the circularity of all kinds of wood wastes. It is also important to note that the use of post-consumer wood as a raw material alleviates the pressure on virgin wood resources, which are then made available to other sectors of the woodworking value chain.

Thank to this dynamic network and the coordination of Rilegno, 1.793.748 million ton of wood waste (50% of which are wooden packaging), three-quarters of the total amount of waste wood collected and recycled in Italy, are sent to recycling for a total number of 100.000 shipments towards the recycling companies that are the backbone of circular economy. Wood wastes, after collection, enter

recycling in 13 plants (2018) distributed all over the national territory, with a major concentration in the North of the country, and with the main destination being panel plants, whose output is then directed to the furniture and furnishing industry.

With the contribution of Rilegno the 62% of wood packaging waste are recovered and headed to mechanical recycling, almost exclusively for the production of wooden conglomerates (mostly particleboard panels and for a smaller part MDF) (Gasperoni, 2019).

2.2.1.4 Finland

The total production of waste wood in Finland was 4,230,770 tons in 2014. The amount of waste wood from packaging is approximately 207,000 ton per year. However, the recovery rate is currently only 15% (approximately 31,000 ton per year) and the remaining fraction is destined for energy purposes 85% (176,000 ton per year) (Manninen, 2015).

The recovery rate of Finland is low in comparison to other countries in Europe due to the fact that the particleboard industry is not very attracted in using these wastes as raw material since higher quality wastes from the forest and sawmill are available in high abundance for the same purpose in this country (Manninen, 2015).

2.2.2 Waste Wood Usage in Composite Wood Based Materials

2.2.2.1 Particleboard

There has been a substantial increase in recycled wood use in particleboard after 1990s. To achieve this, the industry has significantly invested in new equipment and sought to increase the efficiencies of these systems. The use of recycled wood in particleboard has helped considerably in controlling cost and has ensured that particleboard remains a competitive material. This is not possible for MDF in this scale yet (WBPI, 2012).

In 2018, the particleboard industry in the European Panel Federation (EPF) member countries consumed 20.9 million dry tones under bark as wood raw material. In 2018, the share of processed roundwood increased to 31% (29% in 2017), while that of industrial residues dropped compared to the previous year to 29% (37% in 2017). At the same time, the share of recovered wood increased significantly from 34% in 2017 to 40% in 2018 (EPF, 2019).

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	share of roundwood	share of industrial by-products	share of recovered wood
Austria	37%	44%	19%
Belgium	3%	13%	84%
Bulgaria	80%	20%	0%
Czech Republic	16%	64%	20%
Denmark	15%	25%	60%
Estonia	55%	43%	2%
Finland	0%	100%	0%
France	25%	25%	50%
Germany	18%	23%	59%
Greece	87%	13%	0%
Hungary	74%	20%	6%
Italy	3%	4%	93%
Latvia	61%	31%	8%
Lithuania	59%	31%	10%
Norway	3%	97%	0%
Poland	42%	43%	15%
Romania	70%	9%	21%
Slovakia	77%	20%	3%
Spain	45%	33%	22%
Sweden	43%	57%	0%
United Kingdom	19%	38%	43%
TOTAL	31%	29%	40%

Breakdown of the raw wood consumption by the European particleboard industry in major categories, 2018

Despite the legal restrictions concerning added substances and the lack of an efficient collecting system throughout Europe, recovered wood continued to be used by Belgium and Italy for the majority of their wood procurement in 2018. Denmark, Germany, France and United Kingdom also used important quantities of recovered wood, reflecting the encompassing problem of wood availability. Only three countries reported higher usage of roundwood namely Austria, Belgium and Czech Republic compared to 2017. In 2018, roundwood was the main source of raw material for Bulgaria, Greece, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Slovakia and Sweden. Industrial by-products accounted for the main raw material in Austria, the Czech Republic, Finland, Norway, Poland, Romania, Slovenia and Spain.

Breakdown of the raw wood consumption mix by the European particleboard industry, 2018

2.2.2.2 MDF

The raw wood consumption by the European MDF industry increased by 1% in 2018 amounting to 9.7 million dry tonnes under bark. Roundwood maintained its share at 59% compared to 2017. Industrial byproducts, mainly composed of chips, accounted for 41% of the wood

procurement. Recovered wood is still not commonly processed in the European MDF industry (EPF, 2019).

	2015	2016	2017	2018
total raw wood consumption <i>(on the assumption that 1 m³ of MDF requires 0.78 dry tonnes of raw wood)</i>	9,225,000	9,409,000	9,613,500	9,709,635
roundwood	59%	60%	59%	59%
chips	36%	35%	35%	35%
sawdust	4%	5%	5%	5%
other	1%	0%	1%	1%
recovered wood	0%	0%	0%	0%
total	100%	100%	100%	100%

Breakdown of the raw wood consumption of the European MDF industry, 2015-2018

In early 2000s a project demonstrated that it was possible to recycle waste MDF back into 'new' MDF using microwave technology to reprocess the fibres; the key was continuous processing that did not damage the fibres. In 2009 MDF Recovery Ltd (MDFR) was established to exploit this opportunity. The company has developed a novel, proprietary process to recover wood fibre from waste MDF. MDF Recovery is now working with one of the world's leading wood panel board producers to scale up its pilot plant to full industrial systems. However, MDF cannot be recycled to be used in industrial level yet.

3. Composite Wood Based Material Development Activities in Ecobulk

As a composite wood based material, we aimed at manufacturing particleboard for furniture industry which is low (E0) in formaldehyde emission and has high re-manufacturing value.

Wood-based composite materials are mainly made of wood and resin. Wood is a natural resource which can't be easily manipulated. We did our development activities on resins used.

Our first aim was to produce panels from non-formaldehyde resins or at least catch E0 formaldehyde emission level. Our second aim was to produce panels that are easily recyclable with high waste content, especially with high levels of particleboard waste.

Throughout our development activities almost 90 different binder formulations were evaluated. Of those formulations, promising ones were tested in Kastamonu Entegre Adana labs. These trials were made by virgin wood. Binder and chips were blended manually. They all were tested. Around 150 panels were produced and tested.

Best performing 5 formulation² were tested with %100 waste content, simulating different percentages of waste particleboard. When the recycled wood ratio increases, formaldehyde emission of the boards increases. We were able to produce E0 panels with 100% waste. We tested three scenarios with 25%, 35% and 50% particleboard waste content in waste mix. It is known that wood waste used in particleboard production includes particleboard around 20% in Italy and it is much lower in other countries like less than 15% in UK (Circular Economy & Resource Efficiency Experts, 2011). Increasing particleboard waste ratio decreases the internal bond value. Thus, it was important to meet EN312 P2 requirements with higher particleboard waste content. We were able to produce P2 and E0 emission level panels from 100% wood waste with even 50% particleboard waste percentage using our formaldehyde based resin NARY19007. This ensures higher level of utilization of particleboard panels in their end of life. Our non-formaldehyde resin KROL 19007 is very good in formaldehyde emission normally but it has some shortcomings in water resistance. If we can overcome this we can have a non-formaldehyde wood based composite panel produced from 100% waste with high waste particleboard content.

During manufacturing activities, resins were developed by Akzonobel in small batches. We were able to produce 50cmX50cm panels in KEAS labs. We will produce 1.200mmX1.600mmX16mm panels in Fraunhofer WKI facilities with these two formulations. Those panels (if successful) will be used by Moretti in some part of their furniture design.

3.1 Wood Based Panel manufacturing with new innovative binders

[3.1.1 Binder synthesis and formulation](#)

The formulation work of a more sustainable binder was divided into 3 leads:

1. Reduced emission of formaldehyde-based systems
2. Increase renewable raw material content
3. Non-formaldehyde based systems

²

- Formaldehyde based: NARY19006, NARY 19007, NARY 19037, NARY 19038
- No formaldehyde system consisting of 88% renewable raw material: KROL 19007

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The plan was to start with a well-known cost-efficient technology in order to reduce the emission of the boards. From there on, more renewable resources would be incorporated. Finally, non formaldehyde systems, which are the furthest away from the market both regarding price and quality, would be investigated.

AkzoNobel have worked with all 3 leads and Cranfield focused on lead 3.

Lead 1: reduced emission of formaldehyde based systems

In lead 1 a recipe for an existing particle board binder was adjusted with the aim of obtaining a binder with lower formaldehyde emission. Adjustment of the molar ratios, addition order, reaction pH and reaction temperature were made. 22 syntheses were performed by AKZO.

Lead 2: increased amount of renewable raw material

Several renewable resources were evaluated; proteins, starches and lignin. Some of them with modification before use, some of them not. 14 syntheses were performed by AKZO.

For Lead 3: Non-formaldehyde based systems

At AkzoNobel the formaldehyde free systems were synthesized/formulated with dispersion based systems in combination with the renewable raw materials. The systems were evaluated with and without hardener. 50 syntheses/formulations have been made by AKZO. At Cranfield the formaldehyde free systems were of two different kinds, either sodium alginate/bentonite together with a crosslinker of alkali/acid treated wheat gluten as a cross-linker, or a formulation based on olive seed flour. 5 different formulation have been made by Cranfield University and KEAS.

In general physical parameters such as viscosity, solid content and storage stability is always evaluated for adhesives. The desired interval for these parameters is closely connected to what type of application the adhesive will be used for.

Viscosity

In particleboard production viscosities are kept rather low (roughly 150-450 mPas) in order for the adhesive to cover the particles properly and ensure good bonding.

Solid Content

The solid content is in many cases connected to the speed of the system ie the pressing time. In particleboard production, the moisture

content of the binder-covered particles is very important. If it is too high it causes spring-back (the board will not maintain its shape), due to steam blisters when pressed. The lower the solid content of the binder the higher the moisture content of the binder covered particles. Traditional binders have a solid content over 60wt%.

Storage stability

Storage stability is how the viscosity of the binder varies over time. Since the right viscosity is crucial for good bonding, it is important that the viscosity stays fairly constant during its life span. The storage stability must cover the time from synthesis/formulation of the binder to board production including time in storage tanks in production, the time for transportation to the customer as well as the time for storage at the customer before use. Apart from the viscosity it is also important that there is no syneresis or sedimentation during this storage time.

Penetration depth of the binder into the wood

One key factor for achieving good bonding is that the binder penetrates the wood substrate to the right extent. Penetration is dependent on the viscosity of the binder, the difference in surface tension of the binder and the wood substrates as well as the size of the cavities. If there is no penetration into the wood then under penetration will prevent formation of strong wood binder interaction. If the binder on the other hand completely penetrates the substrate, over-penetration, there will only be a thin and weak glue line left.

In order to better understand how penetration and glue line thickness may affect the gluing properties of the newly developed binders, a method was developed to measure and compare the glue-line thickness and penetration of different adhesives using a combination of Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) and light microscopy. An example of a glue line can be seen in Figure 1.

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SEM pictures showing the glue-line thickness and penetration of an amino resin on a wood substrate

Using this method will help in the screening of the new binders, that is, it will help understanding what parameters are important when developing new sustainable binders. Since this is a time consuming it was only used for the most promising systems.

3.1.2 Manufactured panels and evaluation of particleboards according to EN212

Preparation of particle boards at KEAS

Dry wood chips (MC < 4%) were thoroughly mixed with binder and hardener in the equipment for resination.

Wood chips, binder and hardener were put in the resination equipment.

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The resinated chips were thereafter poured into a square 40-by-40 cm mold and pressed using manual force in order to get the wood chips homogeneously distributed in the mold (see Figure 2 and 3).

The mold used for the resinated chips

The board before pressing

The mold was then carefully removed before the manually prepressed board was pressed between two hot metal plates in a press.

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The furniture producer Moretti will use the boards in their furniture production. The desired specification from Moretti is:

- Class P2, according to EN312 but preferably P3
- Emission minimum CARB 2 but preferably non formaldehyde
- Maximize the amount of renewable raw materials

KEAS has the possibility to produce boards of larger size, has a more sophisticated press that resembles the production line and also has the lab equipment for proper resination (applying the binder to the particles) which will give information about both process parameters and the quality of the boards. Hence a more elaborate evaluation package was made for these boards. The tests are a part of EN312 (mentioned previously) which needs to be evaluated in order to establish if the boards reach the quality that the furniture producer Moretti is asking for (P2 or P3).

The tests performed at KEAS can be seen in table.

Property	Method
Density	EN323
Thickness	EN323
Thickness swelling	EN317
Water uptake 24 hours	EN317
Internal bond	EN319
Surface soundness	EN311
Bending strength (MOR)	EN310
Elasticity Modulus (MOE)	EN310
Density Profile	Internal method
Formaldehyde content	EN 12460-5:2016
Emission (ppm)	ASTM D6007
Emission (mg/L)	JIS A1460

Tests performed at KEAS after particleboard production

First trial at KEAS:

For Lead 1 the results showed several promising candidates. 4 of the resins, NARY18089, 90, 91 and 92 gave good glue strength (internal bond, EN319) and storage stability (>3 weeks), and hence they were selected to be tested further at KEAS in Adana.

In the first trial production, dilution of the resins were made in order to reach solid content usually used by KEAS in trial productions, 66% for the core layer and 58.5% for the surface layer. Some of the resins, especially NARY18089, proved hard to dilute and required heating in order to avoid gelation. Therefore dilution was omitted in the second trial. Instead the resins were used with the solid content that they had after synthesis. In all cases, the same hardener system was used, NH₄Cl (26% in water). The press parameters were set according to below table.

Trial	Aimed density (kg/m ³)	Resin dilution	Core: % solid resin on dry wood	Surface:% solid resin on wood dry	Press temp. [°C]	Press time [s]	Press Factor
Trial I	620-640	Yes, both surface and core	10%	8%	200	149	9

Press parameters and resin/wood amounts used in the trial production. The same hardener NH₄Cl (26% in water) was used for all samples as well as the same resin hardener ratio 100:10.5

You can find the test results of trial 1 in figure.

Tests	Unit	Standard	Limits	Sample No			
				89	90	91	92
Thickness	mm	TS EN 324-1	16 ± 0,3	16,39	16,28	16,52	16,48
Density	kg/m ³	TS EN 323	630±10	681	691	691	684
Internal Bond	N/mm ²	TS EN 319	≥ 0,35	0,73	0,44	0,45	0,41
Bending Stress	N/mm ²	TS EN 310	≥ 11	21,37	19,19	18,13	14,65
Elasticity	N/mm ²	TS EN 310	≥ 1600	3780	3532	3820	3680
Screw Holding	N	TS EN 320	450 N	898	924	865	660
Surface Soundness	N/mm ²	TS EN 311	≥ 0,80	1,32	0,98	0,9	0,8
Moisture Content	%	TS EN 322	5 - 13	5,92	5,62	5,88	5,78
Swelling	%	TS EN 317	<15	20,15	26,24	24,37	30,33
Water Absorbtion	%	TS EN 317	max.80	63,1	67,37	76,97	78,17
Formaldehyde Emission	mg/100 gr	TS EN 120	E1: ≤ 8 CARB: ≤ 4 E0: ≤ 2.7	6,06	3,21	4,56	6,36
Formaldehyde Emission	mg/m ² h	TS EN 717-2	E1: ≤ 3.5 E0: ≤ 1.75	2,66	2,00	2,15	2,23

Test Result of Trial 1

All boards pass the P2 and P3 requirements on IB. All boards produced were thicker and denser than expected. Density was highest for NARY18089 and a large standard deviation was observed. NARY18089 also showed the highest IB value which might be due to the high density. These results are usually linked and high IB might be a result

of the high density but the high value for IB of NARY18089 is statistically different from those for NARY18090-92 whereas density values are not.

All samples passed the water absorption test. Again, NARY18089 shows the best value. None of the resins passed the limit for the swelling test. Next step should be to vary the pressing parameters and/or add wax to the board after production to see if this might lower the swelling

The emission results from the first test round were much higher than expected. The aim and hypothesis was that the resins would be E0, but in the perforator test all resins were above the E0-limit. NARY18089, 091 and 092 were even above CARB2 level. In the chamber test the values were within the E1 limit.

As a result, NARY18089 gave the best performance in Trial I in terms of particleboard strength; however, it had the highest emission of the four resins tested. It was speculated that this emission potentially could be lowered by adjusting the pressing parameters, making the pressing time longer.

Based on the result in this first trial, a second round of resins was synthesized at AkzoNobel. The aim was to lower the emission further, while maintaining or increasing the bond strength. Since NARY18089 gave the strongest boards, several of the resins in the second round was based on this resin.

Second trial at KEAS:

In the second trial, seven resins were evaluated. One of these was a reference from KEAS. This was added to be able to confirm that the R&D press used to make the boards at KEAS gave representative strength and performance. The other six resins were resins provided by AkzoNobel. NARY19001 and 19002 were new types of resins with unknown performance in this type of production. NARY19005, 19006 and KROL19006 were modifications of NARY18089. NARY19007 is a resin with known performance. In order to evaluate if the pressing time influenced the emission levels, two different pressing times were used in the second trial, 149 and 223 seconds. The boards pressed for 223 got different density than the ones pressed for 149 seconds, 715 +/- 10 instead of 670 +/- 10 g/m³.

For all formulations as well as the reference the values obtained for Bending strength (MOR), Modulus of elasticity (MOE), Surface Soundness and Internal Bonding (IB) passed all requirements of P2 and P3 boards. The reference system from KEAS performed equally good and also passed the requirements of water absorption and

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thickness swelling. This is a good confirmation that the production process used gives reliable results and that if a product passes the limits it is an interesting candidate to consider when choosing which system to proceed with.

Trial	Aimed density (kg/m ³)	Resin dilution	Core: % resin solid on dry wood	Surface: % solid resin on wood dry	Press temp. [°C]	Press time [s]	Press Factor
Trial II-setting 1	660-680	None	10%	8%	200	149	9
Trial II - setting 2	705-715	None	10%	10%	200	223	9

Press parameters and resin/wood amounts used in the trial 2. The same hardener NH₄Cl (26% in water) was used for all samples as well as the same resin hardener ratio 100:10.5

Tests	Unit	Standard	Limits	660 Board Density						
				Reference	KROL19006	NARY19001	NARY19002	NARY19005	NARY19006	NARY19007
Thickness	mm	TS EN 324-1	16 ± 0,3	16,09	16,05	16,12	16,24	16,17	16,25	16,22
Density	kg/m ³	TS EN 323	630±10	677,73	663,39	677,98	682,77	693,63	684,36	692,77
Internal Bond	N/mm ²	TS EN 319	≥ 0,35	0,74	0,7	0,61	0,58	0,45	0,48	0,97
Bending Stress	N/mm ²	TS EN 310	≥ 11	18,13	17	20,23	22,91	17,43	13,99	17,9
Elasticity	N/mm ²	TS EN 310	≥ 1600	3268,88	3364,63	3537,78	4438,65	4031,7	3358,66	3788,27
Screw Holding	N	TS EN 320	450 N	1010,61	1047,14	1100,45	685,39	640,69	772,05	791,8
Surface Soundness	N/mm ²	TS EN 311	≥ 0,80	1,07	1,55	1,36	1,23	0,87	1,08	1,17
Moisture Content	%	TS EN 322	5-13	5,81	5,47	5,33	5,39	5,38	5,25	5,39
Swelling	%	TS EN 317	<15	15,93	21,35	21,01	22,82	35,72	20,54	22,63
Water Absorbition	%	TS EN 317	max.80	67,6	58,16	59,51	67,28	86,36	84,32	57,38
Formaldehyde Emission	mg/100 gr	TS EN 120	E1: ≤ 8 CARB2: ≤ 4 E0: ≤ 2.7	10,49	2,29	4,03	4,01	1,79	1,52	2,92
Formaldehyde Emission	mg/m ³ h	TS EN 717-2	E1: ≤ 3.5 E0: ≤ 1.75	5,056	1,056	1,138	1,184	0,394	0,564	0,448

Test Results of Trial 2 (660 Density)

Tests	Unit	Standard	Limits	705 Board Density						
				Reference	KROL19006	NARY19001	NARY19002	NARY19005	NARY19006	NARY19007
Thickness	mm	TS EN 324-1	16 ± 0,3	16,3	16,34	16,08	16,37	16,25	16,11	16,29
Density	kg/m ³	TS EN 323	630±10	711,7	774,01	760,04	727,87	707,83	741,55	706,54
Internal Bond	N/mm ²	TS EN 319	≥ 0,35	0,84	0,8	0,74	0,58	0,51	0,64	0,83
Bending Stress	N/mm ²	TS EN 310	≥ 11	17,64	22,9	21,08	16,28	18,86	19,98	24,48
Elasticity	N/mm ²	TS EN 310	≥ 1600	3362,95	3908,46	3937,07	3528,55	3977,45	3731,31	3791,85
Screw Holding	N	TS EN 320	450 N	1096,84	1268,26	1348,86	885,71	1016,92	1305,01	1579,72
Surface Soundness	N/mm ²	TS EN 311	≥ 0,80	1,27	1,25	1,66	1,38	1,14	1,59	1,43
Moisture Content	%	TS EN 322	5-13	5,77	5,07	5,12	5,25	5,03	4,99	4,63
Swelling	%	TS EN 317	<15	9,58	24,23	31,17	28,83	35,96	36,38	23,14
Water Absorbition	%	TS EN 317	max.80	48,13	56,63	62,1	63,84	84,84	66,95	70,32
Formaldehyde Emission	mg/100 gr	TS EN 120	E1: ≤ 8 CARB2: ≤ 4 E0: ≤ 2.7	10,22	2,26	3,06	3,4	2	1,78	2,11
Formaldehyde Emission	mg/m ³ h	TS EN 717-2	E1: ≤ 3.5 E0: ≤ 1.75	3,515	1,213	1,715	0,984	1,358	0,677	0,92

Test Results of Trial 2 (705 Density)

Comparing the results obtained for the boards pressed for 149 s and 223 s as well as a higher resin amount in the core layer, it can be seen that there does not seem to be a clear benefit of using a longer press

time. Also, densities are more scattered in the longer pressing time ($\pm 23 \text{ kg/m}^3$ at 223 s compared to $\pm 10 \text{ kg/m}^3$ at 149).

Internal bond strength and density of boards produced at KEAS in trial II-press time 149 seconds. Limit for IB represented by purple line (P2) and green line (P3)

Internal bond strength and density of boards produced at KEAS in trial II-press time 223 seconds. Limit for IB represented by purple line (P2) and green line (P3)

The larger variation in density for press time 223 seconds makes the IB comparison of these samples less accurate. Still in all cases the strength of the boards produced are above the limit of 0.35 N/mm^2 . Of the AkzoNobel systems, KROL19006 is the strongest in setting 2 (705)

and NARY19007 the strongest in setting 1 (660). In general all systems showed high IB-values.

The formaldehyde content in the different systems is shown in table.

System	Formaldehyde Content, perforator	
	mg/100g	
	TS EN 120	
	E1: ≤ 8 CARB2: ≤ 4 E0: ≤ 2,7	
	660	705
Reference	10.49	10.22
KROL19006	2.29	2.26
NARY19001	4.03	3.06
NARY19002	4.01	3.4
NARY19005	1.79 (2 nd lowest)	2.0 (2 nd lowest)
NARY19006	1.52 (lowest)	1.78 (lowest)
NARY19007	2.92	2.11

The formaldehyde content of the systems according to EN120

Since the emission test in the first trial production was inconclusive and gave an unexpected result, a more thorough investigation was carried out in the second trial production. First, all particle boards were tested in perforator and chamber emission tests immediately after production at KEAS in Adana.

Next, two extra sets of test pieces were prepared and both sets wrapped in plastic foil in order to reduce formaldehyde diffusion. One of the sets was sent to AkzoNobel in Sweden and the other was stored and then sent to another KEAS facility. The two pieces were then analyzed at the same day at both AkzoNobel and KEAS. The aim of these extra tests was to get double control of the emission of the boards. Results are presented below in table.

System	Formaldehyde Emission, chamber, 1 st KEAS		Formaldehyde Emission, chamber, 2 nd KEAS		Formaldehyde Emission, chamber, 1 st AkzoNobel	
	mg/m ² h					
	TS EN 717-2					
	E1: ≤ 3,5 E0: ≤ 1,75					
Density	660	705	660	705	660	705
Reference	5.1	3.5	-	-	3.7	3.9
KROL19006	1.1	1.2	0.9	1.7	0.8	1.0
NARY19001	1.1	1.7	1.1	1.2	1.6	1.0
NARY19002	1.2	1.0	1.3	1.1	0.9	1.3
NARY19005	0.4 (lowest)	1.4	0.2 (lowest)	0.6 (2 nd lowest)	0.4 (2 nd low)	0.4 (lowest)
NARY19006	0.6 (2 nd low)	0.7 (lowest)	0.9 (2 nd low)	1.1	0.3 (lowest)	0.4 (lowest)
NARY19007	0.4	0.9 (2 nd low)	1.6	0.5 (lowest)	0.8	0.6

The formaldehyde emission of the systems according to EN 717-2

Test results vary in between the different labs and between the times of measurement. Sometimes the value for the 705 board is higher than for the 660 board, and the next time it is the opposite result (see for example NARY19001). This makes it hard to pin-point the exact emission level of each system and of the two ways of pressing the boards. Reasons for the fluctuating results might be an effect of the emissions being so low that the wood itself contributes to the observed emission. This can give a source of error that is hard to control and measure. However, some trends can be seen: emissions in the second trial production were over-all lower than in the first. This is in line with the adjustment made to the resins recipes but might also be attributed to the removal of the resin dilution.

The reference provided by KEAS gave high emission levels, not passing E1 on any of the tests. In contrast to this, all EcoBulk resins gave emissions mostly well below the E0 limit. From this point of view, the resin development is a success since low emitting boards have been produced.

If one ignores the actual levels obtained in each test, and just ranks the best and second best performing resin in each set it is clear that NARY19005 and 19006 stands out as the resins that gives the lowest emission values. This is true in almost all tests, no matter the test type, density type or time of measurement. On the other end of the spectra, NARY19001 and 19002, despite in almost all cases giving E0 values are constantly the resins giving the highest emissions

Third trial at KEAS: Non-formaldehyde based resins

The four formulations (KROL 19007, KROL 19008, MISV18169, MISV18181) selected for a lab-scale production trial at KEAS in Adana. You can see the trial calculation (amount of resin and woodchips, moisture of woodchips before and after resination) in table.

You can also see the press parameters and the comment about the board situation after pressing. Except Krol 19007 all resins has a precipitation problem. All the resin were stirred at least for two hours before use.

Formulation	Hardener	Amount hardener (%)	Press factor	Time (seconds)	No of boards	Comment
KROL19007	KROL19000	15	13	247	2	2 board is OK
KROL19008	KROL19000	15	13	247	2	2 board is OK
MISV18169	KROL19000	15	13	247	2	First board had steam blisters, cracks on one side of the board. We make the second board. We have the same blister and cracks problem.
MISV18181	KROL19000	15	13	247	2	First board is OK. Second board had steam blisters, cracks on one side of the board.

Press Parameters for trial 3

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Surface: 10%		Core: 10%		
SAMPLE	KROL19007	solid content resin	0,456	
		solid content wood	0,96	
Wood total	3000 g	solid content hardener	0,25	
Surface	10% solid on solid	Core	10% solid on solid	MC of resinated chips
Amount wood	990 g	Amount wood	2010 g	Surface and core
Amount resin	208,42 g	Amount resin	423,16 g	12,77%
7,5% hardener	15,63 g	7,5% hardener	31,74 g	13,57%
15% hardener	31,26 g	15% hardener	63,47 g	14,35%
SAMPLE	KROL19008	solid content resin	0,465	
		solid content wood	0,96	
Wood total	3000 g	solid content hardener	0,25	
Surface		Core		MC of resinated chips
Amount wood	990 g	Amount wood	2010 g	Surface and core
Amount resin	204,39 g	Amount resin	414,97 g	12,47%
7,5% hardener	15,33 g	7,5% hardener	31,12 g	13,26%
15% hardener	30,66 g	15% hardener	62,25 g	14,04%
SAMPLE	KROL19009	solid content resin	0,468	
		solid content wood	0,96	
Wood total	3000 g	solid content hardener	0,25	
Surface		Core		MC of resinated chips
Amount wood	990 g	Amount wood	2010 g	Surface and core
Amount resin	203,08 g	Amount resin	412,31 g	12,37%
7,5% hardener	15,23 g	7,5% hardener	30,92 g	13,16%
15% hardener	30,46 g	15% hardener	61,85 g	13,93%
SAMPLE	MISV18169	solid content resin	0,441	
		solid content wood	0,96	
Wood total	3000 g	solid content hardener	0,25	
Surface		Core		Worst case
Amount wood	990 g	Amount wood	2010 g	MC of resinated chips
Amount resin	215,51 g	Amount resin	437,55 g	Surface and core
7,5% hardener	16,16 g	7,5% hardener	32,82 g	13,28%
15% hardener	32,33 g	15% hardener	65,63 g	14,09%
				14,89%
SAMPLE	MISV18181	solid content resin	0,449	
		solid content wood	0,96	
Wood total	3000 g	solid content hardener	0,25	
Surface		Core		MC of resinated chips
Amount wood	990 g	Amount wood	2010 g	Surface and core
Amount resin	211,67 g	Amount resin	429,76 g	13,00%
7,5% hardener	15,88 g	7,5% hardener	32,23 g	13,81%
15% hardener	31,75 g	15% hardener	64,46 g	14,60%

Calculation for trail 3

The test results from the evaluation of the particle boards produced at KEAS can be seen in figure.

For all formulations except MISV18169 the Bending strength (MOR), Modulus of elasticity (MOE), Surface Soundness and Internal Bonding (IB) passes all requirements of P2 boards. However, MISV18181, had cracks in the board which indicated too much moisture left in the board or not enough bonding strength at the opening of the press. KROL19007 and KROL19008 did not suffer from these problems.

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Tests	Unit	Standard	Limits	KROL 19007	KROL 19008	MISV 16169	MISV 16181
				Thickness	mm	TS EN 324-1	18 ± 0,3
Density	kg/m ³	TS EN 323	630±10	756	831	705,13	757
Internal Bond- Gebze lab	N/mm ²	TS EN 319	≥ 0,35	0,5	0,41	0,34	0,45
Internal Bond	N/mm ²	TS EN 319	≥ 0,35	0,34	0,48	0,27	0,41
Bending Stress	N/mm ²	TS EN 310	≥ 11	17,48	19,73		
Elasticity	N/mm ²	TS EN 310	≥ 1600	3185	3756		
Screw Holding	N	TS EN 320	450 N	527	423		
Surface Soundness	N/mm ²	TS EN 311	≥ 0,80				
Moisture Content	%	TS EN 322	5-13	8,02	7,85	8,27	8,05
Swelling	%	TS EN 317	<15	43,4	44,3	38,63	35,67
Water Absorbtion	%	TS EN 317	max.80	71,36	74,98	80,16	87,22
Formaldehyde Emission	mg/100 gr	TS EN 120	E1: ≤ 8	0,48	1,37		0,59
			CARB2: ≤ 4				
			E0: ≤ 2,7				
Formaldehyde Emission	mg/m ² h	TS EN 717-2	E1: ≤ 3,5	0,438	0,704	0,515	
			E0: ≤ 1,75				

Test result of the boards in trial 3

The results for absorption and water swelling show, as anticipated, that these types of adhesive systems clearly have difficulties with water resistance.

KROL19008 showed good IB values. This formulation suffered from poor storage stability; if this parameter is easily improved this formulation would be the best option. Otherwise KROL19007 is the best contender. Increasing the solid content is also desired, the moisture content of the resinated chips is too high. With less water in the system the quality (IB) could potentially increase and the press time be reduced.

These systems are formaldehyde free ie there is no added formaldehyde to the formulation and no obvious other formaldehyde source (from decomposition or other reactions). Hence, the formaldehyde visible in the analysis is due to the wood itself.

According to the results from the perforator test the formaldehyde contents for the boards produced with renewable resins are lower than those of the formaldehyde based systems: compare values of 2 mg/100g for formaldehyde based systems to 0.4-0.7 for non-formaldehyde systems.

The emission on the other hand, obtained from chamber test EN717-2, which is roughly 0.4-0.7 mg/m²h for the formaldehyde free formulations, is in the same range as the low formaldehyde systems: 0.2-0.9 mg/m²h.

KROL19008 showed good IB values with small standard deviation. This formulation suffered from poor storage stability; if this parameter is easily improved this formulation would be the best option. Otherwise KROL19007 is the best contender.

Increasing the solid content is also desired, the moisture content of the resinated chips is too high. With less water in the system the quality (IB) could potentially increase and the press time be reduced.

The best formulation with sodium alginate which is developed by Cranfield University was evaluated at KEAS. The solid content of the moisturized chips was higher than desired and so the resulting particle board had cracks in it and could not be evaluated further. A longer pressing time might have helped this somewhat.

Alternatively, the moisturized chips could be dried before press to remove water. But this will require changes in the current particle board process. Different types of additives could be used to increase the water resistance and mechanical properties of the above formulations.

The best current system, the sodium alginate/wheat gluten system, have potential regarding IB and bending strength. The water resistance needs to be improved as well as the processability in larger scale particle board production. In its current form it is not possible to produce large scale boards.

Fourth trial at KEAS: Non-formaldehyde based resins

In trial 3 non-formaldehyde based resins had stability problem. So, we had to stir the resin before use. Normally, Akzo Nobel was adding filler to resin formulation. Filler causes stability problem. In order to solve this problem, Akzo Nobel send resins to KEAS which will be used with filler.

The process parameter, resin type and resin/filler ratio of the trial 4 have seen in table.

Sample	Formulation	Solid Content	Filler/Modifier	Ratio Resin:Filler	Hardener	Amount Hardener	Press Factor	Time (Seconds)
1	KROL19007	46%	YAHA19004	100:10	KROL19000	15	13	247
2	KROL19007	46%	2703	100:10	KROL19000	15	13	247
3	YAHA19006	50%	no filler		KROL19000	15	13	247
4	KROL19007	46%	YAHA19004	100:10	KROL19000	15	10	189
5	KROL19007	46%	2703	100:10	KROL19000	15	10	none
6	KROL19007	46%	YAHA19004-more	100:20	KROL19000	15	10	189
7	KROL19007	46%	YAHA19004	100:10	KROL19000	10	13	247
8	YAHA19006	50%	no filler		KROL19000	15	10	189
9	KROL19007	46%	YAHA19004	100:10	KROL19000	15	10	189

Process parameter and resin/filler ratios in trial 4

When KEAS were pressing the board, there were adhesion problem for all types of the resin. Because of the poor adhesion, board has steam

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blister and crack problems. The test results from the evaluation of the particle boards produced at trial 4 can be seen in below figures. For all samples the IB values were too insufficient. Even Krol 19007 resin which has good result in trial 3 gave us bad result when we mixed it with fillers.

According to the results from the perforator test the formaldehyde contents for the boards produced with renewable resins are in the E0 limit. Just sample 2 couldn't reach the E0 limit.

Tests	Unit	Standard	Limits	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4
				15.05.2019	15.05.2019	15.05.2019	16.05.2019
Thickness	mm	TS EN 324-1	18 ± 0,3	17,67	17,95	18,06	18,19
Density	kg/m ³	TS EN 323	675±10	711	751	746	748
Internal Bond	N/mm ²	TS EN 319	≥ 0,35	0,12	0,14	0,20	0,13
Bending Stress	N/mm ²	TS EN 310	≥ 11	9,91	8,15	10,17	10,62
Elasticity	N/mm ²	TS EN 310	≥ 1600	2525	2464	2426	2329
Screw Holding	N	TS EN 320	500 N	272	179	359	163
Surface Soundness	N/mm ²	TS EN 311	≥ 0,80	0,46	0,70	0,72	0,64
Moisture Content	%	TS EN 322	5-13	6,77	6,69	6,33	7,01
Swelling	%	TS EN 317	<15	32,46	43,54	36,7	73,3
Water Absorbtion	%	TS EN 317	max.80	63,61	61,89	68,21	90,25
Formaldehyde Emission	mg/100 gr	TS EN 120	E1: ≤ 8	2,70	2,78	1,49	2,53
			CARB2: ≤ 4				
			E0: ≤ 2.7				
Formaldehyde Emission	mg/m ² h	TS EN 717-2	E1: ≤ 3.5	0,956	0,816	1,047	0,923
			E0: ≤ 1.75				

Test result of the board which is pressed in Trial 4

Tests	Unit	Standard	Limits	DENEME 5	DENEME 6	DENEME 7	DENEME 8	DENEME 9
				16.05.2019	16.05.2019	15.05.2019	16.05.2019	16.05.2019
Thickness	mm	TS EN 324-1	18 ± 0,3	18,21	18,05	18,06	18,52	18,07
Density	kg/m ³	TS EN 323	675±10	742	676	778	717	744
Internal Bond	N/mm ²	TS EN 319	≥ 0,35	0,10	0,08	0,11	0,21	0,09
Bending Stress	N/mm ²	TS EN 310	≥ 11	12,72	7,59	5,98	10,25	7,45
Elasticity	N/mm ²	TS EN 310	≥ 1600	3204	2344	1751	2576	2143
Screw Holding	N	TS EN 320	500 N	200	205	271	326	203
Surface Soundness	N/mm ²	TS EN 311	≥ 0,80	0,45	0,41	0,65	0,67	0,37
Moisture Content	%	TS EN 322	5-13	7,36	7,61	7,01	7,11	7,58
Swelling	%	TS EN 317	<15	76,66	76,26	73,21	45,53	71,06
Water Absorbtion	%	TS EN 317	max.80	139,34	99,24	96,47	94,89	98,37
Formaldehyde Emission	mg/100 gr	TS EN 120	E1: ≤ 8	1,86	2,03	1,50	1,45	1,90
			CARB2: ≤ 4					
			E0: ≤ 2.7					
Formaldehyde Emission	mg/m ² h	TS EN 717-2	E1: ≤ 3.5	0,794	0,805	1,188	0,684	0,777
			E0: ≤ 1.75					

Figure 14. Test result of the board which is pressed in Trial 4

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Crack and steam blister problem on the samples

This trial was not successful. We decided to continue with previous resin formulation. We wouldn't put any filler to the resin externally.

Fifth trial at KEAS: Non-formaldehyde based resins

The four formulations (KROL 19007, YAHA 19013, YAHA 19023, YAHA 19016) selected for a lab-scale production trial at KEAS in Adana. You can see the trial calculation (amount of resin and woodchips, moisture of woodchips before and after resination) in below table. When we use formaldehyde based resin, we use % 8 resin in core layer. We increased the amount of resin which we use in the core layer to % 10 percent.

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		Surface: 10%			Core: 10%	
SAMPLE	KROL19007		solid content resin		0,456	
			solid content wood		0,97	
Wood total	3000 g		solid content hardener		0,25	
Surface	10% solid on solid		Core	10% solid on solid		MC of resinated chips
Amount wood	990 g		Amount wood	2010 g		Surface and core
Amount resin	210,59 g		Amount resin	427,57 g		12,02%
7,5% hardener	15,79 g		7,5% hardener	32,07 g		12,83%
15% hardener	31,59 g		15% hardener	64,13 g		13,63%
SAMPLE	YAHA 19013		solid content resin		0,448	
			solid content wood		0,97	
Wood total	3000 g		solid content hardener		0,25	
Surface			Core			MC of resinated chips
Amount wood	990 g		Amount wood	2010 g		Surface and core
Amount resin	214,35 g		Amount resin	435,20 g		12,29%
7,5% hardener	16,08 g		7,5% hardener	32,64 g		13,12%
15% hardener	32,15 g		15% hardener	65,28 g		13,92%
SAMPLE	YAHA 19016		solid content resin		0,455	
			solid content wood		0,97	
Wood total	3000 g		solid content hardener		0,25	
						Worst case
Surface			Core			MC of resinated chips
Amount wood	990 g		Amount wood	2010 g		Surface and core
Amount resin	211,05 g		Amount resin	428,51 g		12,05%
7,5% hardener	15,83 g		7,5% hardener	32,14 g		12,87%
15% hardener	31,66 g		15% hardener	64,28 g		13,67%
SAMPLE	YAHA 19023		solid content resin		0,469	
			solid content wood		0,97	
Wood total	3000 g		solid content hardener		0,25	
Surface			Core			MC of resinated chips
Amount wood	990 g		Amount wood	2010 g		Surface and core
Amount resin	204,75 g		Amount resin	415,71 g		11,59%
7,5% hardener	15,36 g		7,5% hardener	31,18 g		12,39%
15% hardener	30,71 g		15% hardener	62,36 g		13,18%

Calculation for trail 5

Akzo Nobel also set us KROL 19000 as hardener. In the trial we used two different amount of hardener which is % 7.5 and % 15.

The test results from the evaluation of the particle boards produced at KEAS can be seen in below figure.

For all formulations the Bending strength (MOR), Modulus of elasticity (MOE), Surface Soundness and Internal Bonding (IB) couldn't pass all requirements of P2 boards. Moreover, boards had cracks in the board which indicated too much moisture left in the board or not enough bonding strength at the opening of the press.

KROL19007 showed better IB values than the other resin formulation. All formulation has poor storage stability. YAHA 19016 was completely solidified when it arrived to KEAS Adana plant. So we couldn't use it

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for board production. KROL 19007 had precipitation problem which is seen in below photo. Due to warm weather condition in August and longtime logistic process, the resins encounter with this kind of agglomeration problem.

The precipitation problem of KROL 19007

TEST NAME	UNIT	STANDARDS	LIMITS	S A M P L E N O					
				KROL 19007 %15 Hardener	YAHA 19013 % 15 Hardener	YAHA 19023 % 15 Hardener	KROL 19007 % 7,5 Hardener	YAHA 19013 % 7,5 Hardener	YAHA 19023 % 7,5 Hardener
Thickness	mm	TS EN 324-1	18 ± 0,3	18,17	18,16	18,15	18,44	18,52	18,11
Density	kg/m ³	TS EN 323	685±10	722	708	718	740	737	7,34
Internal Bond	N/mm ²	TS EN 319	≥ 0,35	0,27	0,20	0,25	0,19	0,11	0,23
Bending Stress	N/mm ²	TS EN 310	≥ 11	11,32	9,92	10,02	8,22	9,20	9,53
Elasticity	N/mm ²	TS EN 310	≥ 1600	2638	2360	2482	2436	2430	2593
Screw Holding	N	TS EN 320	450 N	264	210	313	198	143	190
Surface Soundness	N/mm ²	TS EN 311	≥ 0,80	1,06	0,67	1,06	0,67	0,56	0,85
Moisture Content	%	TS EN 322	5-13	9,02	8,72	8,58	8,30	8,39	8,48
Swelling	%	TS EN 317	<15	38,04	36,66	38,63	50,74	50,96	51,40
Water Absorbtion	%	TS EN 317	max.80	96,0	81,1	74,7	100,63	99,15	117,36
Formaldehyde Emission	mg/100 gr	TS EN 120	E1: ≤ 8 CARB2: ≤ 4 E0: ≤ 2,7	0,82	0,78	1,00	0,57	0,74	0,62

The test results from the evaluation of the particle boards produced at trial 5

The results for absorption and water swelling show, as anticipated, that these types of adhesive systems clearly have difficulties with water resistance. If we look formaldehyde emission test result, there is no added formaldehyde to the formulation and no obvious other formaldehyde source (from decomposition or other reactions). Hence, the formaldehyde visible in the analysis is due to the wood itself. All samples met the E0 formaldehyde emission requirement.

After this trial, we decided to continue with KROL 19007 for non-formaldehyde based resin. We will make a trial again with KROL 19007.

3.2 Manufacturing and re-manufacturing performance of new panels

3.2.1 Recyclability test results of panels produced with developed binder

In section 2.2.1 and 2.2.2 we have seen waste wood usage dynamics in wood based panel production. Wood waste is highly coming from demolition, construction and wood packaging. The highest wood waste utilization ratio in particleboard manufacturing is experienced in Italy, where 95% of wood comes from wood waste, and %50 of mechanically recycled wood in this country is wooden packaging. Wooden pallet is the main wooden packaging waste. It is known that wood waste used in particleboard production includes particleboard around 20% in Italy and it is much lower in other countries like less than 15% in UK (Circular Economy & Resource Efficiency Experts, 2011). So we aimed at reaching low formaldehyde emissions E0 with 100% waste. During trials, we increased particleboard waste ratios in the waste mix from %25 to %50.

Sixth trial at KEAS:

Trial 6 was the first trial which the recycled wood particle was used. The five formulations (NARY 19006, NARY 19036, NARY 19037, NARY 19038, NARY 19007) selected for a lab-scale production trial at KEAS in Adana. Due to warm weather condition in August and longtime logistic process NARY 19037, NARY 19038, NARY 19007 were completely solidified. These resins couldn't be used for board production. NARY 19006 and NARY 19036 could be used for the trial.

The amount of resin, chemicals and recycled wood particle that was used for surface and core layer are seen in below table. In this trial, each resin has used for two different recycled wood particle ratio. In the first trial, % 100 recycled wood particle was used for board production. Another ratio was % 25 recycled wood and % 75 percent virgin wood.

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NARY 19006 (%100 Recycled wood)		NARY 19036 (%100 Recycled wood)	
SL Recycled %100	798,8	SL Recycled %100	798,8
CL Recycled %100	1651	CL Recycled %100	1651
SL Resin	154,05	SL Resin	154,05
SL Water	22,01	SL Water	19,29
SL Hadener	5,69	SL Hadener	5,69
CL Resin	227,47	CL Resin	232,15
CL Hadener	18,37	CL Hadener	18,37
Pres factor	9	Pres factor	9

The amount of resin, chemicals and recycled wood particle (% 100 recycled)

During the resination of wood particles with NARY 19036, the wood particles had flocculation problem. The reason would be insufficient resin distribution.

Test result of boards which is produced with recycled wood can be seen in below.

TESTS	UNIT	LIMITS	ECOBULK TRIAL 6 TEST RESULT					
			UF YL 650 1,22 Reference % 100 Recycled	NARY 19006 % 100 Recycled	NARY 19036 % 100 Recycled	UF YL 650 1,22 Reference % 25 Recycled	NARY 19006 % 25 Recycled	NARY 19036 % 25 Recycled
Thickness	mm	16 ± 0,3	15,84	15,85	15,81	16,11	16,07	16,05
Density	kg/m³	685±10	798	760	741	707	716	703
Internal Bond	N/mm²	≥ 0,35	1,10	0,34	0,42	1,38	0,46	0,48
Bending Stress	N/mm²	≥ 11	17,98	5,82	7,44	14,96	7,45	9,44
Elasticity	N/mm²	≥ 1600	2532	1722	1577	2174	1870	2214
Screw Holding	N	500 N	1302	461	497	1137	730	574
Surface Soundness	N/mm²	≥ 0,80	1,42	1,24	1,39	1,38	1,45	1,40
Moisture Content	%	5-13	6,88	5,31	5,54	6,17	5,59	5,67
Swelling	%	<15	10,19	13,4	14,6	13,64	22,09	25,48
Water Absorbtion	%	max.80	13,71	23,22	40,43	50,11	79,98	73,92
Formaldehyde Emission (PERFARATOR)	mg/100 gr	E1: ≤ 8	6,43	3,02	2,42	8,64	1,84	2,01
		CARB2: ≤ 4						
		E0: ≤ 2.7						

Test Result of Trial 6

According to test results, NARY 19006 and NARY 19036 have lower internal bond values than KEAS reference resin for the same recycled wood ratio. **When recycled wood ratio decreases in the board, the internal bond value increases.** Recycled wood may include resin, so there is a lack of hydroxyl group in wood particle for bonding.

At % 25 recycled ratio, NARY 19006 and NARY 19036 have negative results in terms of swelling. The reason is virgin wood particles which were used wouldn't be applied paraffin.

For % 100 recycled wood ratio, NARY 19036 fulfill the E0 requirement and NARY 19006 meet CARB2 requirements. For % 25 recycled wood ratio, Both NARY 19006 and NARY 19036 meet the E0 requirement. **When the recycled wood ratio increases, formaldehyde emission of the boards increases.**

Due to hot weather condition in August, the trial 6 has just been done with two resin. So we decided to repeat this trial. NARY 19006, NARY 19037, NARY 19038 and NARY 19007 will also be used in Trial 7.

Seventh trial at KEAS:

In trial 7, all boards were produced with % 100 recycled wood. The difference was the type of the recycled wood. The particleboard recycled wood particles and wooden pallet recycled wood particles were mixed with different ratios. The five formulations (NARY 19006, 1.22 mole UF (KEAS reference resin), NARY 19037, NARY 19038, NARY 19007) selected for a lab-scale production trial 7 at KEAS in Adana.

	% 25 Particleboard recycled / % 75 wooden pallet recycled	% 35 Particleboard recycled / % 65 wooden pallet recycled	% 50 Particleboard recycled / % 50 wooden pallet recycled
1.22 mole UF	2 boards	2 boards	2 boards
NARY 19006 - MUF	2 boards	2 boards	2 boards
NARY 19007 - MUF	2 boards	2 boards	2 boards
NARY 19037 - MUF	2 boards	2 boards	2 boards
NARY 19038 - MUF	2 boards	2 boards	2 boards

The Plan of Trial 7

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TESTS	UNITS	LIMITS	% 25	% 35	% 50	% 25	% 35	% 50
			NARY 19006	NARY 19006	NARY 19006	NARY 19007	NARY 19007	NARY 19007
THICKNESS	mm	16 ± 0,3	16,72	16,50	16,43	16,34	16,64	16,72
DENSITY	kg/m ³	680±10	671	674	669	699	675	697
INTERNAL BOND	N/mm ²	≥ 0,35	0,51	0,46	0,42	0,79	0,65	0,88
BENDING STRESS	N/mm ²	≥ 11	10,08	9,59	7,95	13,92	11,02	10,22
ELASTICITY	N/mm ²	≥ 1600	2189	2379	2301	2640	2226	2025
SCREW HOLDING	N	450 N	801	446	646	851	822	980
MOISTURE CONTENT	%	5-13	6,53	6,28	7,28	6,59	6,66	7,74
SWELLING	%	<15	29,56	26,95	8,8	36,67	19,30	24,68
WATER ABSORPTION	%	max.80	69,46	72,33	39,67	60,64	62,77	62,18
Formaldehyde Emission (PERFARATOR)	mg/100 gr	E1: ≤ 8 CARB2: ≤ 4 E0: ≤ 2.7	1,65	1,58	1,33	2,41	2,17	1,67

Test Results of NARY 19006 and NARY 19007

Test result of boards which is produced with NARY 19006 and NARY 19007 can be seen in table. For NARY 19006 and NARY 19007, Water Absorption, Modulus of elasticity (MOE), Internal Bonding (IB) could pass all requirements of P2 boards. NARY 19007 showed better IB values than the other resin formulation. **When particle board recycled wood ratio increases in the board, the internal bond value decreases.** Recycled wood may include resin, so there is a lack of hydroxyl group in wood particle for bonding

When particleboard recycled wood particles ratio increases inside the board, swelling test results get better. This is an expected situation because particle board recycled wood particles comprise paraffin. Both NARY 19006 and NARY 19007 meet the E0 requirement. When the particleboard recycled wood ratio increases, formaldehyde emission of the boards decreases.

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TESTS	UNITS	LIMITS	% 25	% 35	% 50	% 25	% 35	% 50
			NARY 19037	NARY 19037	NARY 19037	NARY 19038	NARY 19038	NARY 19038
THICKNESS	mm	16 ± 0,3	16,78	16,89	LACK OF RESIN	16,71	17,46	17,55
DENSITY	kg/m ³	680±10	687	686		665	642	6
INTERNAL BOND	N/mm ²	≥ 0,35	0,40	0,29		0,15	0,06	0,06
BENDING STRESS	N/mm ²	≥ 11	9,90	9,32		3,84	6,64	6,31
ELASTICITY	N/mm ²	≥ 1600	2387	2055		1357	1754	1534
SCREW HOLDING	N	450 N	811	473		348	204	146
MOISTURE CONTENT	%	5-13	6,38	5,96		6,73	6,21	8,05
SWELLING	%	<15	29,86	32,71		45,37	57,63	39,31
WATER ABSORPTION	%	max.80	62,86	79,71		85,32	82,56	80,62
Formaldehyde Emission (PERFARATOR)	mg/100 gr	E1: ≤ 8 CARB2: ≤ 4 E0: ≤ 2.7	3,12	2,05		3,7	Boards couldnt be cut for the test because of adhesion problem.	

Test Results of NARY 19037 and NARY 19038

Test result of boards which is produced with NARY 19037 and NARY 19038 can be seen in table. For NARY 19037 and NARY 19038, Water Absorption, Modulus of elasticity (MOE), Internal Bonding (IB) couldn't pass all requirements of P2 boards. NARY 19037 showed better IB values than NARY 19038 but those values were not enough to pass the requirement of P2 boards. Both NARY 19037 and NARY 19038 cannot meet the E0 requirement.

In trial 7 the most successful **formaldehyde based** resin was NARY 19007. For the next step, this resin will be used in pilot production.

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TESTS	UNIT	STANDARD	Limits	TEST RESULTS														
				% 25 Reference UF YL	% 35 Reference UF YL	% 50 Reference UF YL	% 25 NARY 19006	% 35 NARY 19006	% 50 NARY 19006	% 25 NARY 19007	% 35 NARY 19007	% 50 NARY 19007	% 25 NARY 19037	% 35 NARY 19037	% 50 NARY 19037	% 25 NARY 19038	% 35 NARY 19038	% 50 NARY 19038
THICKNESS	mm	TS EN 324-1	16 ± 0,3	16,70	16,47	16,41	16,72	16,50	16,43	16,34	16,64	16,72	16,78	16,89	We didnt have enough resin for pressing samples.	16,71	17,46	17,55
DENSITY	kg/m³	TS EN 323	680±10	668	656	640	671	674	669	699	675	697	687	686		665	642	6
INTERNAL BOND	N/mm²	TS EN 319	≥ 0,35	0,81	0,66	0,88	0,51	0,46	0,42	0,79	0,65	0,88	0,40	0,29		0,15	0,06	0,06
BENDING STRESS	N/mm²	TS EN 310	≥ 11	12,09	11,98	11,81	10,08	9,59	7,95	13,92	11,02	10,22	9,90	9,32		3,84	6,64	6,31
ELASTICITY	N/mm²	TS EN 310	≥ 1600	2130	2044	1956	2189	2379	2301	2640	2226	2025	2387	2055		1357	1754	1534
SCREW HOLDING	N	TS EN 320	450 N	1100	520	1258	801	446	646	851	822	980	811	473		348	204	146
SURFACE SOUNDNESS	N/mm²	TS EN 311	≥ 0,80	1,09	0,82	1,23	1,06	1,00	1,08	1,08	1,23	1,60	1,08	0,96		0,70	0,61	0,57
MOISTURE CONTENT	%	TS EN 322	5-13	7,26	7,11	7,09	6,53	6,28	7,28	6,59	6,66	7,74	6,38	5,96		6,73	6,21	8,05
SWELLING	%	TS EN 317	<15	14,26	26,36	14,16	29,56	26,95	8,8	36,67	19,30	24,68	29,86	32,71		45,37	57,63	39,31
WATER ABSORPTION	%	TS EN 317	max.80	56,10	66,17	57,25	69,46	72,33	39,67	60,64	62,77	62,18	62,86	79,71		85,32	82,56	80,62
Formaldehyde Emission (PERFORATOR)	mg/100 gr	TS EN 120	E1: ≤ 8 CARB2: ≤ 4 E0: ≤ 2.7	13,97	10,82	13,14	1,65	1,58	1,33	2,41	2,17	1,67	3,12	2,05	3,7	-		
Formaldehyde Emission (GAS ANALYSIS)	mg/m³h	TS EN 717-2	E1: ≤ 3.5 E0: ≤ 1.75	9,21	8,57	10,15	1,45	0,87	1,03	0,67	1,81	1,49	1,08	0,76	0,97	1,84	2,48	
Resin Type.				Reference UF YL 1,22			NARY 19006			NARY 19007			NARY 19037			NARY 19038		

Test results of formaldehyde based formulations compared with reference resin

Eighth trial at KEAS: Validation of KROL 19007

One **non formaldehyde** formulation (KROL 19007) was selected for a lab-scale production trial at KEAS in Adana. You can see the trial calculation (amount of resin and woodchips, moisture of woodchips before and after resin application) in table. KROL 19000 was added inside the resin as hardener. (% 7.5 w)

Surface: 10%		Core: 10%		
SAMPLE	KROL19007	solid content resin	0,456	
		solid content wood	0,97	
Wood total	3000 g	solid content hardener	0,25	
Surface	10% solid on solid	Core	10% solid on solid	MC of resinated chips
Amount wood	990 g	Amount wood	2010 g	Surface and core
Amount resin	210,59 g	Amount resin	427,57 g	12,02%
7,5% hardener	15,79 g	7,5% hardener	32,07 g	12,83%
15% hardener	31,59 g	15% hardener	64,13 g	13,63%

Calculation for trail 8

TESTS	UNITS	STANDARDS	Limits	TEST RESULTS	
				REFERENCE UF YL	KROL 19007 % 7,5 Hardener
THICKNESS	mm	TS EN 324-1	18 ± 0,3	17,90	18,07
DENSITY	kg/m ³	TS EN 323	680±10	677	688
INTERNAL BOND	N/mm ²	TS EN 319	≥ 0,35	0,69	0,40
BENDING STRESS	N/mm ²	TS EN 310	≥ 11	16,08	18,09
ELASTICITY	N/mm ²	TS EN 310	≥ 1600	3673	5279
SCREW HOLDİNG	N	TS EN 320	450 N	1140	694
SURFACE SOUNDNESS	N/mm ²	TS EN 311	≥ 0,80	1,18	1,11
MOISTURE CONTENT	%	TS EN 322	5-13	6,74	7,06
SWELLİNG	%	TS EN 317	<15	15,00	28,22
WATER ABSORBİTION	%	TS EN 317	max.80	56,85	46,39
Formaldehyde Emission (PERFARATOR)	mg/100 gr	TS EN 120	E1: ≤ 8 CARB2: ≤ 4 E0: ≤ 2.7	8,77	3,55 /4,19
Formaldehyde Emission (GAS ANALYSIS)	mg/m ² h	TS EN 717-2	E1: ≤ 3.5 E0: ≤ 1.75	4,13	1,11

Test results of KROL 19007 and KEAS refrence resin

Test result of boards which is produced with KROL 19007 and KEAS refrence resin can be seen in table. For KROL 19007 resin the Bending strength (MOR), Modulus of elasticity (MOE), Surface Soundness and

Internal Bonding (IB) passes all requirements of P2 boards. If we compare the KROL 19007 with UF reference resin. We can easily say that KROL 19007 has positive effect on elasticity of the board.

The results for absorption and water swelling show, as anticipated, that these types of adhesive systems clearly have difficulties with water resistance. Water resistant additive can be added to the resin formulation. (ex: PMDI)

According to the results from the perforator test the formaldehyde contents for the boards produced with renewable resins are upper than 2.7 mg/100g. So, KROL 19007 meet the CARB 2 requirement for this trial. This was not expected situation because there was no any added formaldehyde source to the resin formulation. Probably, measurement error would occur during the formaldehyde emission test.

The emission on the other hand, obtained from chamber test EN717-2, which is roughly 1.11 mg/m²h for the formaldehyde free formulations. So, this result meet the E0 requirement.

As a brief, KROL 19007 has promising results. This resin will be used in pilot production as non-formaldehyde resin.

Next Step:

We will continue with one formaldehyde based and one non-formaldehyde based resin NARY 19007 and KROL 19007 respectively. We will produce 1.200mm X 1.600mm X 16mm panels in Fraunhofer WKI facilities with these two formulations.

4. Furniture Development Activities in Ecobulk

4.1 Ecobulk furniture design approach

The main objective for furniture is to create long life products and then to postpone their disposal as much as possible; once reached that point, is fundamental to favor reuse and recovery even before recycling.

The design approach is based on a modular solution implying 2 standard sized parallelepipeds: the first advantage is less waste during production, since we avoid oversize. The cubes are joined using a fastening system that allows for disassembly into individual cubes that

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could be replaced if they are damaged rather than the whole furniture piece.

The final design is obtained after several modifications, in order to guarantee best ergonomic, comfort and safety performances.

Bed and library composition

Concerning the material selection, the most practical solution has been identified, namely the utilization of particleboard panels coated with melamine paper; it is also possible to replace the outer layer with a laminated material for greater resistance over time, but production could be more complex in terms of costs and practical problems.

Desk, chair and little cabinet composition

Some products, such as the bed and especially the chair, will also show some additions to ensure greater comfort for the end user: for this reason, the introduction of fabrics and upholstered parts created with recycled fabrics that do not require the use of screws and / or adhesives for integration into furnishings.

Moretti Compact also uses neutral colours (white, light blue, grey) that would remain in fashion and increase the potential of second life of the product; moreover, further properties are versatility and adaptability: a cube that starts as library could be re-used and/or recovered for other applications such as bed, chairs and tables and vice versa.

4.2 Recyclability and re-usability of developed furniture

The target furniture output is classified as panel furniture where particleboard content is more than %95 of total material used. In terms of technical properties, the utilization of lower/no formaldehyde particle board (also being developed in ECOBULK and used for some Moretti products), beyond the positive aspects regarding emissions, enables higher quality of recycled content in recycled particleboard obtained after the dismissing of the prototypes (easily recyclable thanks to their melamine finish).

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Furthermore, the prototypes realized by Moretti Compact are already produced by using 100% recycled particleboard, exploiting the efficient recycling system currently implemented in Italy and coordinated by the national consortium Rilegno.

As anticipated, some products, such as the bed and especially the chair, will also show some additions to ensure greater comfort for the end user: for this reason, the introduction of fabrics and upholstered parts created with recycled and recyclable textiles that do not require the use of screws and / or adhesives for integration into furnishings.

Final versión of prototypes

For the next few months, a new formulation will also be introduced by NTT to implement further types of panels made with non-woven layers; the idea is to produce some prototypes at Moretti also using these innovative solutions.

Beyond these technical features, the scope of reuse and recovery can be reached by experimenting a new business model (for a SME) already hypothesized by IKEA (Fordaq, 2019), namely the leasing: in this way, furniture can be provided for rent for a certain period; at the conclusion, the end user can decide to purchase the products or, alternatively, to give them to the producers. This latter, will rent them again as 2nd hand products to other end-users. The solution, probably more suitable for temporary residences such as dormitories, is under experimentation in order to evaluate the economic viability for an SME.

5. Planned Activities

We will produce composite wood based panels with formaldehyde based NARY 19007 and non-formaldehyde based KROL 19007 resins. We will produce 1.200mmX1.600mmX16mm panels in Fraunhofer WKI facilities with these two formulations. Those panels (if successful) will be sent to Moretti for new furniture design. Furniture demo activities will go on without waiting. We will provide 100% recycled 4.250mmX2.120mmX16mm panels to Moretti from KEAS Italy factory for current design if necessary.

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